

1 **Seismic damage assessment of a crude oil hydrodesulphurisation unit.**

2 **Part II: hazard-consistent fragility assessment**

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5 **Abstract**

6 This study presents a methodology for developing hazard-consistent component-specific
7 fragility functions for a system of interconnected industrial assets. The approach begins with
8 the seismic hazard assessment of the area of interest carried out for an intensity measure that
9 can be used as a practical yet reasonably accurate statistical predictor of the response of such
10 assets to ground motions of different severity. The response is evaluated via nonlinear time
11 history analyses with an ensemble of ground motions whose spectral content is consistent with
12 the hazard assessed for the site. This methodology is applied to a hydrodesulphurisation unit
13 of a crude oil refinery located in a high-seismicity industrial area of Greece. The exposure
14 model and the unit assets' models have already been presented in detail in the companion paper.
15 The case study shows that even low-to-moderate intensity ground motions pose a non-
16 negligible probability of damage to assets such as pumps, heat exchangers, high-temperature
17 separators, liquid storage tanks, and piping system. The proposed methodology lays the
18 groundwork for comprehensive system-level seismic risk and resilience assessment studies that
19 evaluate the impact on refinery units or on the entire facility, as will be demonstrated in an
20 upcoming dedicated study.

21 **Keywords**

22 Crude oil refinery, hydrodesulphurisation unit, seismic hazard analysis, seismic fragility,
23 ground motion hazard consistency

24 **1 Introduction**

25 The seismic fragility and risk assessment of industrial facilities requires modelling complex,
26 interconnected systems, each one comprising multiple components. For such systems and their
27 subsystems, the decision of how to separate or aggregate the underlying assets is critical, as it
28 can significantly impact the final risk estimates. Herein, we focus on the fragility assessment
29 of the critical unit in a crude oil refinery presented in our companion paper [1]. Fragility is a
30 mandatory step in seismic risk assessment as it is the bridge between ground motion intensity
31 and the actual structure's response, which can be mapped into a repair/replacement cost and,
32 in the case of system, a loss due to disruption of operations. Moreover, in the context of
33 industrial facilities, seismic damage can be mapped into physical consequences such as fire or
34 explosion (see, for example, the case of liquid storage tanks in [2]), which not only impact
35 human health and the environment but may also trigger damage propagation in the refinery in
36 a domino fashion.

37 Following an approach similar to building portfolios, on one end of the spectrum an industrial
38 facility can be discretised to its constituent independently-responding structures, splitting them
39 according to the intuition of a structural engineer. This is typical when adopting fragility

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40 functions based on expert judgment and empirical observations, as these are normally
41 generated along the same lines (e.g., [3-6]). This path makes perfect sense for many self-
42 standing assets, such as liquid storage tanks. It is also a natural approach when taking the
43 analytical path for fragility computation via numerical models. In such cases, the focus has
44 often been on tracking cascading effects to monitor sequences of failures among adjacent assets
45 (e.g., [7-9]).

46 The path to take becomes less straightforward for complex agglomerations of interconnected
47 pieces of equipment and assets linked by piping across one or more nearby structures as
48 investigated, for example, in [10]. In such cases, one can still opt to consider each structure as
49 a separate asset with all consequences aggregated within a single asset-level fragility. For
50 example, this was the approach followed by Karagiannakis et al. [11], where adjacent complex
51 equipment-supporting structures were modelled separately, incorporating components such as
52 piping, reactors, and heat exchangers into a single fragility pertaining to each asset in question.
53 As always, when consolidating the response of multiple components into a single fragility
54 function, simplicity comes at the expense of resolution. This approach limits the ability to
55 pinpoint the specific impacts of component-level (e.g., individual reactor or exchanger)
56 disruptions to facility functionality and downtime, especially for a less-than-catastrophic
57 seismic event. In this regard, the ideal approach would be the one of Vathi et al. [12] who
58 explicitly modelled assets together with their interconnecting piping network into a single
59 large-scale model. While comprehensive, this method is not easily scalable due to its high
60 computational demands.

61 Our recommendation takes a balanced approach, aiming for more detailed results than those of
62 Karagiannakis et al. [11], while retaining the computational simplicity that is lacking in the
63 work of Vathi et al. [12]. We strive to provide a full view of each separate structure and its
64 critical components within an interconnected functional unit of a crude oil refinery, creating a
65 foundation for multiple levels or approaches of analysis that account for all potential asset- or
66 component-level disruptions. Specifically, structurally-independent assets are individually
67 considered and analysed using separate numerical models, while taking into account any nested
68 mechanical equipment or internal non-structural elements of the assets. To integrate these
69 assets, a reduced-order model is employed for the piping network, connecting all components
70 into a cohesive functional system. Furthermore, rather than relying on generic ground motions,
71 we employ a carefully selected set of hazard-consistent (i.e., representative of the site's hazard)
72 ground motions for conducting nonlinear time history analyses of all the industrial assets and
73 producing fragility functions, as demonstrated, e.g., by [13-15]. This hazard-consistent fragility
74 assessment methodology is demonstrated for a hydrodesulphurisation unit, whose functionality
75 and exposure model has already been detailed in the companion paper [1].

76 **2 Seismic hazard analysis, ground motion intensity measure choice and hazard-** 77 **consistent record selection**

78 The first step of any seismic risk assessment study is the evaluation of the hazard posed by
79 earthquake at the site of interest. In this study, a probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA,
80 [16]) was conducted using the OpenQuake Engine [17] for Elefsina, Greece, west of Athens,
81 at coordinates 23.51° longitude and 38.04° latitude, on a rock site, where the refinery under
82 investigation is located. This location is characterised by high seismic hazard and intense
83 industrial activity, particularly in the petrochemical sector. The seismic hazard of the area is
84 dominated by the faults in the Corinth Gault located to the south-southwest [18]. It is noted
85 that shallow crustal events having been recorded within a few kilometres of the site. The

86 analysis utilised the area source model developed for the 2013 European Seismic Hazard model
87 (ESHM13, [19]) and the ground motion prediction equation proposed by Boore and Atkinson
88 [20]. A V_{S30} of 800m/s is adopted for the site.

89 The objective is to evaluate the seismic performance of an entire functional unit of the refinery
90 rather than focusing solely on individual assets. This requires analysing multiple
91 interconnected assets with diverse geometry and dynamic properties. In this context, selecting
92 ground motion intensity measures (IMs – e.g., spectral accelerations at different vibration
93 periods, PGA, PGV) to be used for fragility computations that are optimal for efficiency and
94 sufficiency [21] is particularly challenging. Optimising this process for each asset would
95 require selecting asset-specific IMs, which would add complexity by requiring a PSHA that
96 incorporates cross-correlation relationships between different dependent IMs. These
97 complexities extend further to, first, the selection of multiple ensembles of hazard-consistent
98 ground motions for fragility computations and, second, to structural response analyses carried
99 out with different ground motion sets specific for each structure. This process would result in
100 a set of fragility curves, all anchored to different IMs, to be integrated into a single risk
101 assessment study. To avoid these challenges, a practical compromise is to use a single albeit
102 suboptimal IM. This approach simplifies seismic hazard calculations, ground motion record
103 selection, fragility curve development and, in the hand, risk calculations while maintaining an
104 acceptable level of accuracy given the feasible number of nonlinear analyses budgeted for
105 developing fragility curves.

106 A common choice for such an IM is the “asset-agnostic” peak ground acceleration (PGA).
107 However, a more effective alternative is the average spectral acceleration (*AvgSa*) [22-27].
108 *AvgSa* is calculated as the geometric mean of spectral accelerations over a specific period
109 interval tailored for the structure(s) at hand, a range that in this study spans from 0.1 to 1.0s
110 with a step of 0.1s, i.e., *AvgSa*[0.1s: 0.1s: 1.0s] that is abbreviated as *AvgSa* hereinafter for
111 the sake of simplicity. This range is representative of most industrial components analysed,
112 given their relatively low fundamental vibration periods due to high stiffness and design
113 assumptions of elastic behaviour under near-design-level events. *AvgSa* for the [0.1s, 1.0s]
114 range has been widely used in seismic fragility assessments of industrial assets (e.g., [13-15,
115 28]). Kohrangi et al. [29], for instance, demonstrated that the use of *AvgSa* with a
116 representative period range can be a valid yet efficient alternative to the use of a vector of IMs
117 when performing the seismic risk assessment of 3D structures. This is an important
118 consideration when one considers the challenges of including in practical applications vector
119 IMs in both hazard assessment and response evaluation. The hazard curve for Elefsina,
120 corresponding to *AvgSa*, is shown in Figure 1.

121

Figure 1. Hazard curve for site of interest for a V_{S30} of 800m/s.

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124 The Multiple Stripe Analysis (MSA) method [30] is employed for evaluating the seismic
 125 performance of the assets and consequently estimating the relationship between the selected
 126 IM (here *AvgSa*) and the engineering demand parameters, EDPs (e.g., inter-story drift for
 127 buildings or floor acceleration for non-structural components). Within MSA, dynamic analyses
 128 are performed at a specific set of IM levels (or stripes), and a unique suite of recorded ground
 129 motions is selected for each stripe [31] by employing the Conditional Spectrum (CS) approach
 130 [32, 33]. The CS target spectrum for each stripe is defined using all the magnitude-distance
 131 scenarios that contribute to the hazard of the site based on hazard disaggregation. This is the
 132 so-called “exact” CS [34], which is a refinement of the CS defined considering only the mean
 133 magnitude and distance of the earthquake scenarios controlling the hazard at each stripe.

134 Specifically, the eleven *AvgSa* levels listed in Table 1 are chosen to describe the hazard curve
 135 for the site. Then, a suite of 40 pairs of ground motion records was selected based on the
 136 GMRotD50 that better match the mean and dispersion of the target CS at each stripe. These
 137 records were selected from the database developed by García de Quevedo Iñárritu et al. [35],
 138 which includes ground motions from the NGA-West2 database [36], the ESM database [37],
 139 the New Zealand Strong-Motion database [38], and the NEar-Source Strong-Motion database
 140 (NESS) [39]. In total, 440 pairs of records were selected for the eleven *AvgSa* levels
 141 considered to assess the response of all interconnected assets. It is noted that the HDS unit
 142 footprint is of the order of 280×200m, therefore uniform soil conditions throughout the unit are
 143 assumed, neglecting any spatial variability of the ground motion (e.g., due to decoherence).
 144 Consequently, the same ground motions are applied to all the assets in analysis. It is the case
 145 that some refineries are located at sites with heterogeneous soil conditions. In such instances,
 146 the analyst should factor in the effects of this variability, such as phase shifts and site effects,
 147 in the assessment, and modify the ground motion for each asset accordingly. However, this
 148 does not apply to the HDS unit being analysed.

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152

153 Table 1. Hazard levels selected for the stripes of MSA [λ_{AvgSa} : mean annual rate of exceedance, P_{50} :
 154 probability of exceedance in 50 years, T_R : mean return period].

Hazard level	λ_{AvgSa} (yr ⁻¹)	P_{50}	T_R (yr)	$AvgSa$ (g)
1	0.0465	90.0%	22	0.082
2	0.0241	70.0%	42	0.117
3	0.0139	50.0%	72	0.156
4	0.0071	30.0%	140	0.217
5	0.0045	20.0%	224	0.271
6	0.0021	10.0%	475	0.381
7	0.0010	5.0%	975	0.518
8	0.0006	3.0%	1642	0.636
9	0.0004	2.0%	2475	0.740
10	0.0003	1.5%	3308	0.818
11	0.0002	1.0%	4975	0.933

155

156 Several studies (e.g., [34, 40]) emphasise the importance of ensuring hazard consistency in
 157 ground motion inputs when selecting representative ground motions to assess the future
 158 performance of a structure at a specific location. This is because fragility curves are
 159 traditionally based on a single IM, say PGA or spectral acceleration at a given period, but other
 160 characteristics of the ground motion (e.g., duration, spectral content at other periods than that
 161 of the selected IM) that depend on the parameters of the causative earthquakes affect the
 162 response. The distribution of such additional parameters depends on the scenarios controlling
 163 the hazard at the site. A generic selection of ground motions would have, in general, a different
 164 distribution of all other characteristics and, therefore, this discrepancy would bias the resulting
 165 fragility function. In the context of this study, hazard consistency is achieved when the IM-
 166 based hazard curves empirically derived from the response spectra of the set of ground motions
 167 selected for evaluating structural response do not significantly deviate from the corresponding
 168 hazard curves obtained for the site via PSHA. Hazard consistency for other ground motion
 169 characteristics different from response spectral ordinates of the motions (e.g., duration) is not
 170 enforced here. Figure 2 proves the hazard consistency achieved for the set of ground motions
 171 selected based on the IM of choice, namely $AvgSa[0.1s, 0.1s, 1.0s]$ and, as an illustrative
 172 example, for the lower and upper bound ordinates of the range, namely $Sa(0.1s)$ and $Sa(1.0s)$.
 173 The consistency is evidenced by the alignment between the empirical curves extracted from
 174 the ground motions and the PSHA-based curves, following the procedure in [34].

175

176 Figure 2. Hazard consistency with respect to spectral shape of selected records [dashed lines: hazard
177 curves directly derived from PSHA, solid lines: empirical hazard curves from selected records].

178 3 Hydrodesulphurisation (HDS) unit and assets at risk

179 The HDS unit of a typical crude oil refinery is adopted as a case study to demonstrate the
180 methodology for producing component-specific and location-specific (ensured by the ground
181 motions set consistent with the site hazard) seismic fragility functions. In the HDS process, the
182 sulphur content of petroleum products is reduced to satisfy the mandated threshold, e.g., per
183 EU Directive 2009/30/EC [41]. The assets comprising the HDS unit under analysis are listed
184 in Table 2, while the schematic plan of the unit is offered in Figure 3. The input material, stored
185 in two liquid storage tanks (TK-01 and TK-02), is transported to the heat exchangers (E-01, E-
186 02A&B, E-03A&B), which are located in an equipment-supporting building, and the furnace
187 (H-01) for increasing its temperature before entering the reactors (R-01 and R-02). The reacted
188 material, after cooling in two heat exchangers (E-03A&B), passes through the high-
189 temperature separator (V-01), which divides the hydrogen sulphide from the fluid. The latter is
190 delivered to the stripper (C-01) for removing light fractions. The product is then stored in two
191 additional tanks (TK-03 and TK-04) after being cooled in a heat exchanger (E-01). The pumps
192 in the unit (P-01, P-01S, P-02, P-02S) maintain the circulation of the fluid, delivering it to each
193 unit asset at the required pressure. A detailed overview of the HDS operation, the assets in
194 analysis, and their respective numerical models are presented in the companion paper [1]. The
195 unit assets are numerically represented by simplified models, while taking into account directly
196 or indirectly any nested pieces of machinery (e.g., heat exchangers located on the equipment-
197 supporting building) or internal non-structural components (e.g., lining of furnace). For the
198 piping system model, in particular, single-mass representations of the assets are employed in
199 tandem with a full 3D model of the pipes connecting them to ensure a proper consideration of
200 dynamic effects of the vibrating structures on the interconnecting pipes. Our motivation for this
201 stems from the path taken by Vathi et al. [12], further corroborated by historical evidence (e.g.,
202 [42-47]) whereby failure patterns to tanks and adjacent elements indicate a dynamic interaction.

203

Table 2. Assets comprising the HDS unit (after Grajales-Ortiz et al. [1]).

Asset description	Asset ID
Liquid storage tanks	TK-01, TK-02, TK-03, TK-04
Pumps	P-01, P-01S, P-02, P-02S
Heat exchangers	E-01, E-02A, E-02B, E-03A, E-03B
Furnace	H-01
Reactors	R-01, R-02
High temperature separator	V-01
Stripper	C-01

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Figure 3. Schematic plot plan of the HDS unit (adapted from Grajales-Ortiz et al. [1]).

207 4 Damage states and MSA results

208 Results from MSA are utilised for producing fragility functions that express the conditional
 209 probability of exceedance of a damage state, DS, (e.g., slight damage, moderate damage,
 210 extensive damage, partial or total collapse) for different levels of IM experienced. The
 211 attainment of a DS is expressed in terms of thresholds of relevant EDPs, for example, inter-
 212 story drift in the case of a building structure or floor acceleration for a piece of equipment

213 mounted on it. As discussed later, to achieve more realistic results during fragility
 214 computations, the EDP thresholds triggering a DS are considered as random variables rather
 215 than constants. The DSs considered for each asset are described subsequently in the relevant
 216 subsections.

217 4.1 Liquid storage tanks

218 The DSs for atmospheric unanchored liquid storage tanks are the so-called “component-level”
 219 DSs of Bakalis et al. [48] listed in Table 3. Since these DSs are not sequential nor mutually
 220 exclusive, we decided to identify them with letter-based indices, i.e., DS_{SL}, DS_{BP}, DS_{EFB},
 221 instead of serial numbers, such as DS1, DS2, and DS3.

222 Table 3. Liquid storage tanks: DS classification and associated EDPs [DS_{SL}: sloshing DS, DS_{BP}: base
 223 plate DS, DS_{EFB}: elephant’s foot buckling DS].

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	—
DS _{SL}	Roof damage due to exceedance of available freeboard, d_f ($d > d_f$)	Maximum convective wave height (d)
DS _{BP}	Fracture of the tank’s base plate ($\theta_{pl} > 0.4$ rad)	Base plate rotation (θ_{pl})
DS _{EFB}	Elephant’s foot buckling due to exceedance of critical buckling limit, σ_{EFB} ($\sigma_m > \sigma_{EFB}$)	Meridional stress of the tank’s shell (σ_m)

224

225 The seismic response of liquid storage tanks is heavily influenced by their fill ratio (see
 226 discussion in [1, 49, 50]). Uncertainty in fill ratio is incorporated in this study by including
 227 three characteristic distinct fill ratios per tank type: 90% (roughly full tank), 60% (half-filled
 228 tank), and 30% (roughly empty tank). Results from MSA for the tanks at a 90% fill ratio, which
 229 is considered the most seismically vulnerably one, are shown in Figure 4 and discussed herein.
 230 The median value of the EDP corresponding to the threshold of each respective DS is also
 231 shown in Figure 4. The left column refers to TK-01, TK-02, and TK-03, and the right column
 232 refers to TK-04, which differs only because of its denser content. Note that the median EDP
 233 threshold is not constant for DS_{EFB} because the critical buckling limit changes for each ground
 234 motion (in general decreasing with increasing seismic intensity), as it depends on the wall
 235 pressure estimated from structural analysis; this median EDP threshold for tanks at a 90% fill
 236 ratio varies between 0, for stronger ground motions, to 60 MPa, for weaker ground motions.
 237 Results from MSA for the tanks at 60% and 30% fill ratios are included in the supplementary
 238 material (see Figure A-1 and Figure A-2 in Appendix). Also, MSA results for the other
 239 considered assets (i.e., pumps, equipment-supporting building, heat exchangers, furnace,
 240 reactors, stripper, piping system) are included in the Appendix.

241 As seen in Figure 4(a) and 4(b), the estimated maximum convective weight heights for all tanks
 242 are in most cases lower than the respective median EDP threshold. From Figure 4(c) and 4(d),
 243 it is interesting to note that the base plate rotation (θ_{pl}) saturates at around 0.6rad for both tank
 244 type. This saturation is due to membrane action in the base plate as, at some point in the time
 245 history analysis, the bottom of the tanks stops deforming and it is dragged upwards by the
 246 uplifting wall (see, for example, Bakalis et al. [48]). From an analysis of Figure 4(e) and 4(f),
 247 the meridional stress of the tank’s shell (σ_m) appears to saturate as well, but this effect depends

248 on the density of the contained liquid, as it occurs at around 15 MPa for TK-01, TK-02, and
 249 TK-03 (tanks containing either naphtha or gasoline, with a density of 750 kg/m^3), and at around
 250 25 MPa for TK-04 (containing gasoil, with a density of 845 kg/m^3).

251
 252 Figure 4. Tanks MSA results per EDP (left: TK-01, TK-02, and TK-03; right: TK-04) at a 90% fill ratio:
 253 (a),(b) Height of sloshing wave for DS_{SL}; (c),(d) base plate rotation for DS_{BP}; (e),(f) wall meridional
 254 stress for DS_{EFB}. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines the onset of each
 255 damage state; it is constant for DS_{EFB} as it changes with the ground motion and the intensity (the median
 256 values per stripe are shown) [d : maximum convective wave height, θ_{pl} : base plate rotation, σ_m :
 257 meridional stress of the tank's shell].

258 4.2 Pumps

259 Pumps, as well as heat exchangers, and the high temperature separator, are considered
260 acceleration-sensitive non-structural components. Two DSs are considered for these assets, as
261 listed in Table 4. The median capacity of their anchorage systems is estimated by assuming a
262 design as per the recommendations of EN 1998-1:2004 [51], Clause 4.3.5 “Non-structural
263 elements”. For all the non-structural components, a component importance factor of 1.50 is
264 adopted as proposed by EN 1998-1:2004 for tanks and vessels containing toxic or explosive
265 substances. Also, a behaviour factor equal to 1.00 is considered for all non-structural
266 components, implying an elastic design of anchorages, which is in accordance to the
267 operational requirements of the assets. Specifically for pumps, an overstrength factor of 1.10
268 in both directions is assumed. More details on the capacity calculation can be found in Kazantzi
269 et al. [14]. In analysing all acceleration-sensitive components, anchorage failure is attained
270 when demands exceeds capacity either in the x or in the y direction, whichever occurs first.

271 Table 4. Pumps, heat exchangers, and high temperature separator: DS classification and associated
272 EDPs.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	—
DS1	Anchorage failure	Peak Component Acceleration (<i>PCA</i>)

273

274 The MSA results for pumps, as well as the DS1 median EDP threshold (i.e., the capacity of the
275 anchorage) in each global direction, are shown in Figure A-3 (Appendix). Note that, as demand
276 and capacity of acceleration-sensitive non-structural components may be different for the two
277 x and y global directions, the Peak Component Acceleration (PCA) is recorded in both
278 directions for each component. Also, because all pumps (i.e., P-01, P-01S, P-02, and P-02S)
279 are located at the ground level, the seismic demand of all pumps is the same and, therefore, a
280 single set of results is presented for all. Given that pumps are modelled as elastic 3D single-
281 mass systems, PCA is equal to the ground spectral acceleration for the fundamental period of
282 the pump. Also note that PCA values typically saturate when the component anchorage starts
283 yielding; this saturation is not captured due to the component elasticity assumption, and
284 therefore an “almost linear” increase in PCA with the IM is observed in Figure A-3. Actually,
285 we would be observing a perfectly linear increase with IM if we had used the same set of
286 records successively scaled up in each stripe; instead, to ensure hazard consistency we utilised
287 different ground motion sets per stripe, hence the “almost linear” behaviour.

288 4.3 Equipment-supporting building and heat exchangers

289 The equipment-supporting building structure itself is considered to be fairly ductile and, thus,
290 subject to drift-sensitive structural damage without consideration for brittle failures. The DSs
291 for the building, which are listed in Table 5, are based on Kazantzi et al. [14] and the provisions
292 of EN 1998-1:2004.

293

294 Table 5. Industrial building: DS classification and median values of the EDP associated to the onset of
 295 each DS.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	-
DS1	$IDR > 1\%$	Interstorey Drift Ratio (<i>IDR</i>)
DS2	$IDR > 2\%$	Interstorey Drift Ratio (<i>IDR</i>)
DS3	$IDR > 4\%$	Interstorey Drift Ratio (<i>IDR</i>)

296

297 By inspecting the MSA results for the equipment-supporting building shown in Figure A-4, it
 298 can be concluded that the building is not expected to experience seismic damage as it is heavily
 299 overdesigned, in other words, little (if any) structural damage is anticipated for such structures
 300 even during strong ground shaking [14]. Therefore, for the purposes of risk assessment, there
 301 is no need to consider fragility functions for the equipment-supporting building itself. In the
 302 parlance of FEMA P-58 [52], the equipment-supporting building can be considered a “rugged”
 303 component. It is noted that for sites with a higher seismic hazard and/or applications where unit
 304 safety under extremely rare ground motions for the assessment (e.g., with a return period of
 305 10,000yrs or more) is a concern, developing fragility functions for such assets could be
 306 valuable, given the potential consequences of their damage or failure on refinery operations.
 307 However, even in these scenarios, the contribution of these assets to the overall risk of the unit
 308 being taken out of operation remains secondary.

309 The DSs relative to the heat exchangers, which are acceleration-sensitive non-structural
 310 component, are listed in Table 4. The anchorage of the heat exchangers within the equipment-
 311 supporting building is assumed to have been originally designed based on standard practice
 312 [14], treating all components as if they were located at the top of the building, irrespective of
 313 their actual elevation. Additional overstrength factors of 1.50 and 1.20 are adopted for the
 314 calculation of the anchorage system capacity in the x and y directions, respectively; these
 315 factors stem from material overstrength and additional joint overdesign. MSA results for the
 316 heat exchangers are presented in Figure A-5. Given the regularity and torsionally-insensitive
 317 response of the equipment-supporting building, floor accelerations are consistently similar
 318 within each floor; thus, the demands of E-02A versus E-02B, as well as the demands of E-03A
 319 versus E-03B, are almost identical. Because of this symmetry, Figure A-5 presents only one set
 320 of results for E-02A&B and E-03A&B. Conversely, PCAs increase significantly with height,
 321 particularly for E-03A&B in the x direction, for which the heat exchanger’s period (0.15s) is
 322 closer to the structure’s fundamental period (0.21s). Same as with the pumps, the assumption
 323 of an elastic supporting structure leads for the heat exchangers to an almost linear rise in PCA
 324 demand with increasing *AvgSa* levels.

325 4.4 Furnace

326 Two different sets of DSs are considered for the furnace. The first set of DSs, listed in Table 6,
 327 is associated to damage of the furnace structure itself and to the exceedance of the drift capacity
 328 for connected piping. DS1 is related to operability of the furnace, and the 0.5% limit of top
 329 drift ratio is adopted after EN 1998-6:2005 [53]. DS2 is related to damage to the furnace’s
 330 insulation lining, and the 1.2% limit of the intersegment drift ratio is also adopted after EN
 331 1998-6:2005. DS3 is related to buckling failure of the furnace and is checked according to EN
 332 1993-1-6:2007 [54] provisions. The local buckling parameter, R_c , is calculated as:

$$R_c = \left(\frac{\sigma_E}{\sigma_R}\right)^{k_x} + \left(\frac{\tau_E}{\tau_R}\right)^{k_\tau} \quad (1)$$

333 where σ_E is the axial buckling stress demand; σ_R is the axial buckling stress resistance; τ_E is
 334 the shear buckling stress demand; τ_R is the shear buckling stress resistance; k_x , k_τ are the
 335 combination factors for the interaction of axial compression and shear. As in Karaferis et al.
 336 [13] for steel process towers and chimneys, the peak value of R_c is computed at each time step
 337 and compared to the threshold value in Table 6 to evaluate whether DS3 is reached.

338 The second set of DSs, outlined in Table 7, pertains to the damage of the piping supports inside
 339 the convection section of the furnace. This set of DSs is specifically included because the high
 340 stiffness of the furnace could cause significant acceleration demands for internal piping
 341 supports in this section. In contrast, the piping in the radiant section (see Grajales-Ortiz et al.
 342 [1]) is fixed to the walls and vibrates in unison with them. Given the substantial stiffness of
 343 this structure, this section is excluded from the evaluation of damage to piping supports. The
 344 capacity of piping supports is calculated using the non-dissipative design approach of prEN
 345 1998-4:2021 [55] and considering the piping as a non-structural element, as discussed in
 346 Kazantzi et al. [56]. A single capacity value is calculated for an elevation corresponding to the
 347 top of the convection section. For the demand, a worst-case scenario is assumed where the
 348 piping in the convection section is tuned to the supporting structure (furnace). The PCA is
 349 computed based on the mass of the piping within the convection section and the assumed
 350 vibration period. Since capacity and demand are different for the two global directions x and y ,
 351 we produced a different set of PCAs depending on the direction in analysis.

352 MSA results for the first set of DSs of the furnace are shown in Figure A-6 while those for the
 353 second set of DSs can be found in Figure A-7. Comparing the results in Figure A-6 with the
 354 thresholds in Table 6 reveals that demands are significantly smaller than capacities, eliminating
 355 the need for fragility functions. Similarly, a comparison of the results in Figure A-7 with the
 356 estimated capacities (170.4m/s^2 and 169.9m/s^2 for the x and y directions, respectively) shows
 357 that also in this case capacities are significantly greater than demands. Therefore, no fragility
 358 functions are needed for this second set of DSs either. These findings indicate that, for the
 359 *AvgSa* range that can be experienced at this site, the probability of exceeding the evaluated
 360 DSs is practically zero and, therefore, the furnace is not expected to be damaged and can be
 361 considered as rugged.

362 Table 6. Furnace: Set of DS related to the structure and connected piping: classification and median
 363 values of the EDP associated to the onset of each DS.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	—
DS1	Damage to connected piping ($TDR \geq 0.5\%$)	Top Drift Ratio (TDR)
DS2	Damage to the liner ($IDR \geq 1.2\%$)	Intersegment Drift Ratio (IDR)
DS3	Local buckling of shell ($R_c \geq 1.0$)	Local buckling parameter (R_c)

364 Table 7. Furnace: Set of DS related to the piping supports inside the convection section: classification
 365 and associated EDPs.
 366

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	—
DS1	Damage to piping supports in convection section	Peak Component Acceleration (PCA)

367

368 4.5 Reactors and stripper

369 The reactors and the stripper are treated as steel process towers and the DSs in consideration
 370 are listed in Table 8 after [13]. Results from MSA for the reactors and stripper are shown in
 371 Figure A-8. From Figure A-8(a), it can be seen that DS1 is expected to be exceeded mostly for
 372 *AvgSa* values higher than 0.6g. At the same time, the exceedance of DS2 is rare, even for the
 373 highest *AvgSa* levels employed, as shown in Figure A-8(b). These observations are consistent
 374 with the analysis in Karaferis et al. [13].

375 Table 8. Reactors and stripper: DS classification and median values of the EDP associated to the onset
 376 of each DS.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	—
DS1	Damage to connected piping ($TDR \geq 0.5\%$)	Top Drift Ratio (TDR)
DS2	Local buckling of shell ($R_c \geq 1.0$)	Local buckling parameter (R_c)

377

378 4.6 High temperature separator

379 To evaluate the DSs relative to the high temperature separator (see Table 4), the capacity of the
 380 anchorage system is calculated assuming overstrength factors of 1.50 and 1.20 for the global *x*
 381 and *y* directions, respectively, after Kazantzi et al. [14]. Same as pumps, the high temperature
 382 separator is located on the ground. Results from MSA for the high temperature separator are
 383 shown in Figure A-9. Again, the assumption of elasticity leads to an unbounded increase in
 384 PCA demand as *AvgSa* levels increase, consistent with the behaviour of pumps and heat
 385 exchangers.

386 4.7 Piping

387 The DSs in Table 9 proposed by Vathi et al. [12] for piping segments subjected to earthquake
 388 loading are adopted here. Specifically, two different modes of failure are considered: the first
 389 is related to a tensile fracture and the second is related to a local compressive/buckling failure.
 390 A yield strain limit ϵ_Y of 0.21% marks the initiation of DS1 for both modes. The onset of DS2
 391 occurs when either the plastic strain limit reaches 0.5% in tension, or when the compressive
 392 strain ϵ_c exceeds the resistance (ϵ_{Cu}), a value that depends on the pipe diameter and thickness.
 393 Finally, DS3 is attained at an ultimate strain limit equal to 3% either in tension or in
 394 compression. Again, recall that the values listed above are median values of the random
 395 variables representing the respective capacities; during the calculations, the variability of those
 396 capacities is accounted for.

397 Based on the DSs listed above, a set of system-level DSs is defined to describe overall piping
 398 system damage: DS1, DS2, or DS3 is reached when the corresponding DS occurs in any piping
 399 segment. Although some components are linked by multiple piping lines, the system operates
 400 in series. Thus, a DS violation for the entire system occurs when the first piping segment
 401 reaches the corresponding DS.

402

403

404 Table 9. Piping: DS classification and median values of the EDP associated to the onset of each DS
 405 (after Vathi et al., [12]).

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
DS0	—	—
DS1	$0.21\% < \varepsilon_t \leq 0.5\%$ or $0.21\% < \varepsilon_c \leq \varepsilon_{Cu}^\dagger$	Tensile and compressive strains ($\varepsilon_t, \varepsilon_c$)
DS2	$0.5\% < \varepsilon_t \leq 3\%$ or $\varepsilon_{Cu} < \varepsilon_c \leq 3\%$	Tensile and compressive strains ($\varepsilon_t, \varepsilon_c$)
DS3	$\varepsilon_t > 3\%$ or $\varepsilon_c > 3\%$	Tensile and compressive strains ($\varepsilon_t, \varepsilon_c$)

$^\dagger \varepsilon_{Cu}$: compressive strain resistance

406

407 For each piping segment, whether straight parts or fittings, we recorded the maximum
 408 longitudinal strain in tension and compression. For visualisation, the maximum longitudinal
 409 strains are plotted in groups of pipe diameters; this is because, as mentioned earlier, ε_{Cu}
 410 depends on the pipe characteristics. Results from MSA for the piping system are presented in
 411 Figure A-10 for the tensile strain and in Figure A-11 for the (absolute) compressive strain.
 412 Excessive strains beyond 5% (not shown in these figures) were observed for several high
 413 intensity records. It is interesting to note that 12” and 24” diameter pipes tend to experience
 414 significantly larger axial strains compared to 6” and 10” diameter pipes. This is consistent with
 415 expectations, as the d_m/t ratio, which is one of the parameters governing the pipe structural
 416 response, is greater in 12” and 24” diameter pipes (see Grajales-Ortiz et al. [1]). Also, because
 417 the flexibility characteristic k_B is greater in 12” and 24” diameter pipes compared to 6” and
 418 10” diameter pipes, one would also expect larger axial strains in 12” and 24” fittings compared
 419 to 6” and 10” fittings.

420 5 Fragility functions

421 The construction of analytical fragility functions is thoroughly documented in the international
 422 literature (e.g., [31, 57-62]). Fragility functions in terms of ground motion IM for each DS are
 423 defined as:

$$P[DS|IM] = P[D > C_{DS}|IM] \quad (2)$$

424 where D is the demand in terms of an EDP, and C_{DS} is the EDP capacity threshold associated
 425 to the DS of interest. Assuming a lognormal distribution [63] of the ground motion capacity
 426 IM_c (here expressed in terms of $AvgSa$) required to violate the DS of interest, namely of the
 427 EDP value corresponding to the onset of that DS, fragility functions are expressed by the
 428 equation:

$$P[D > C_{DS}|IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln IM - \ln IM^{50}}{\beta}\right) \quad (3)$$

429 where IM^{50} is the median value of IM_c , and β is the logarithmic standard deviation of IM_c .

430 As mentioned earlier, the EDP capacity is considered to be a random variable rather than a
 431 constant. Fragility functions are produced for each DS of each asset of the HDS unit. During
 432 fragility calculations, for each ground motion of every strip in the MSA, 200 realisations of the
 433 capacity are performed for each component according to the following scheme:

- 434 • For liquid storage tanks, capacities are sampled from lognormal distributions with
 435 dispersions equal to 0.20, 0.51, and 0.31 for DS_{SL} , DS_{BP} , and DS_{EFB} , respectively, as
 436 suggested by Bakalis et al. [48], and median thresholds listed in Table 3.

- 437 • For pumps, heat exchangers, and the high temperature separator capacities are sampled
438 from a normal distribution with a 20% coefficient of variation (CoV), following
439 suggestions from Kazantzi et al. [14]. For each realisation two values of the capacities are
440 sampled, one for each principal direction (x and y); zero correlation is assumed between
441 said capacities.
- 442 • For steel process towers, values of the capacities are sampled from a normal distribution
443 with a 20% CoV, following suggestions from Karaferis et al. [13].
- 444 • For the piping system, values of the capacities are sampled from a normal distribution with
445 a 20% CoV after Gresnigt and Karamanos [64] (see, also, discussion in Melissianos et al.
446 [65]).

447 As mentioned above, no damage is expected for the equipment-supporting building and the
448 furnace at the ground motion levels of interest at the refinery site (i.e., rugged components);
449 therefore, their probability of failure is assumed to be zero.

450 The maximum likelihood approach is adopted for fitting the lognormal fragility model [31].
451 The estimates of the median (IM^{50}) and logarithmic dispersion (β) of IM_c for each asset and
452 DS are presented in Table 10. The resulting lognormal fragility functions are shown by dashed
453 and dotted lines in Figure 5 to Figure 12 for the liquid storage tanks, pumps, heat exchangers,
454 steel process towers (i.e., reactors and stripper), high temperature separator, and piping system,
455 respectively. The cross, circles and triangle markers in those figures represent the exceedance
456 probability estimates extracted from each one of the MSA stripes. The fitted lines, however,
457 represent reasonably well all the empirical probability estimates with the exception of the DS_{BP}
458 case, as discussed below.

459 Table 10. Median (IM^{50}) and dispersion (β) estimates of the fragility functions for the different DSs of
460 the assets present in the HDS unit.

Component	DS _{SL}		DS _{BP}		DS _{EFB}	
	IM^{50} (g)	β	IM^{50} (g)	β	IM^{50} (g)	β
TK-01/02/03 (90% fill ratio)	3.83	0.85	0.40	1.10	1.02	0.28
TK-04 (90% fill ratio)	3.83	0.85	0.38	1.10	0.62	0.31
TK-01/02/03 (60% fill ratio)	–	–	0.65	0.83	1.16	0.29
TK-04 (60% fill ratio)	–	–	0.61	0.84	0.95	0.28
TK-01/02/03 (30% fill ratio)	–	–	6.51	1.19	4.14	0.63
TK-04 (30% fill ratio)	–	–	5.37	1.14	1.94	0.39
Component	DS1					
	IM^{50} (g)			β		
Pumps	0.29			0.74		
E-01	0.23			0.44		
E-02A&B	0.58			0.45		
E-03A&B	0.42			0.47		
Component	DS1		DS2			
	IM^{50} (g)	β	IM^{50} (g)	β		
R-01/02, C-01	0.91	0.33	2.03	0.40		
Component	DS1					

	$IM^{50} (g)$		β			
V-01	0.23		0.44			
Component	DS1		DS2		DS3	
	$IM^{50} (g)$	β	$IM^{50} (g)$	β	$IM^{50} (g)$	β
Piping system	0.52	0.76	0.62	0.70	0.97	0.94

461

462

463 Figure 5. Fragility functions for the liquid storage tanks at a 90% fill ratio: (a) TK-01, TK-02, and TK-
 464 03; (b) TK-04 [the dotted line refers to the original lognormal fit for DS_{BP} , and the solid line refers to
 465 the empirical CDF for DS_{BP}].

466

467 Figure 6. Fragility functions for the liquid storage tanks at a 60% fill ratio: (a) TK-01, TK-02, and TK-
 468 03; (b) TK-04 [the dotted line refers to the original lognormal fit for DS_{BP} , and the solid line refers to
 469 the empirical CDF for DS_{BP}].

470

471 Figure 7. Fragility functions for the liquid storage tanks at a 30% fill ratio: (a) TK-01, TK-02, and TK-
 472 03; (b) TK-04. No empirical CDF for DS_{BP} is used as the maximum likelihood fit is reasonably accurate.

473

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Figure 8. Fragility function for the pumps (P-01, P-01S, P-02, P-02S).

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Figure 9. Fragility functions for the heat exchangers: (a) E-01; (b) E-02A&B; (c) E-03A&B.

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478

Figure 10. Fragility functions for the reactors (R-01, R-02) and the stripper (C-01).

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Figure 11. Fragility function for the high temperature separator (V-01).

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Figure 12. Fragility functions for the piping system.

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The results from the fragility analysis are summarised as follows:

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- For liquid storage tanks at a 90% fill ratio (see Figure 5), the lognormal fit tends to overestimate the occurrence of DS_{BP} for both low and high $AvgSa$ levels, while underestimating its occurrence for intermediate $AvgSa$ levels (i.e., between 0.25g and 0.50g). In other words, the observed saturation in the base plate plastic rotation makes the common assumption of lognormality of the random variable IM_c not appropriate in this case. This is especially true at lower quantiles where frequent low-amplitude ground motions are predicted by the lognormal capacity model to generate non-negligible economic losses for $AvgSa$ values as low as 0.05g, which are not supported by evidence. Hence, instead of using the lognormal fit for this damage case, we propose the use of an empirical CDF constructed by interpolating the empirical probability of DS_{BP} from the different stripes, as shown in Figure 5. The same empirical CDF approach is applied to tanks at a 60% fill ratio (see Figure 6) while the lognormal fit for the for DS_{BP} capacity of

496 tanks with a 30% fill ratio (see Figure 7) appears sufficiently accurate and, therefore, no
 497 empirical fitting is used. It is also interesting to note that DS_{EFB} is very sensitive to
 498 variations in substance densities between the analysed tanks, as shown in Table 10 and
 499 Figure 5. In contrast, DS_{BP} is largely unaffected by fluid density differences, with nearly
 500 identical median estimates in both cases. Table 10 and Figure 5 also indicate that DS_{SL} is
 501 less critical than DS_{BP} or DS_{EFB} for the analysed tanks. With a 60% and 30% fill ratio, the
 502 probability of DS_{SL} is zero, making the consideration of the corresponding fragility
 503 functions unnecessary.

- 504 • In the piping system (Figure 12), individual fragilities for different segments are not shown
 505 due to their interactions. A segment's failure probability may seem to decrease as *AvgSa*
 506 levels increase, but this is because another segment has already failed earlier, reducing
 507 strain on the evaluated segment. Instead, we decided to plot a set of charts showing the
 508 contribution of each pipe category (grouped by diameter) to the piping system-level DSs,
 509 as shown for DS1 in Figure 13, for DS2 in Figure 14, and for DS3 in Figure 15. The largest
 510 contribution to system-level DS1 (Figure 13) comes from 10" pipes, followed by 12" pipes,
 511 as they typically reach DS1 before other diameters. For DS2 (Figure 14), 10" pipes
 512 dominate over all other categories. In DS3 (Figure 15), damage from 12" pipes is most
 513 significant, though 10" pipes also play a major role in the system's failure. In summary, 10"
 514 pipes are the most critical pipe category for the system-level DS1 and DS2, while the failure
 515 of the 12" pipes is the most likely cause of the system-level DS3.

516

517 Figure 13. Contribution of DS1 damage to different pipe categories (diameters) to the overall piping
 518 system-level DS1.

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520 Figure 14. Contribution of DS2 damage to different pipe categories (diameters) to the overall piping
 521 system-level DS2.

522

523 Figure 15. Contribution of DS3 damage to different pipe categories (diameters) to the overall piping
 524 system-level DS3.

- 525 • Overall, pumps, heat exchangers, and the high-temperature separator emerged as the assets
 526 most prone to earthquake-induced damage. Liquid storage tanks and the piping system also
 527 merit special consideration due to the potential facility-wide consequences associated with
 528 their loss of functionality, particularly for possible business interruption of the HDS unit.
 529 Reactors and the stripper, on the other hand, showed comparatively lower probability of
 530 damage, particularly for their highest damage state DS2.

531 **6 Intensity-based assessment**

532 To illustrate the application of the produced fragility functions, we selected the following four
 533 *AvgSa* intensity levels: 0.16, 0.38, 0.52, and 0.74g, corresponding to 50%, 10%, 5%, and 2%
 534 probability of exceedance in 50 years (i.e., 42, 475, 975, and 2,475-yr return periods),
 535 respectively. This exercise is performed to offer a scenario-based assessment, i.e., an intensity-
 536 based assessment, which is useful as a preliminary qualitative identification of the most critical
 537 assets and essentially those assets that could contribute more in case of failure to business
 538 disruption. Moreover, stakeholders are more familiar with this type of assessment, which can
 539 also contribute to the development of emergency response planning and design of mitigation
 540 actions.

541 For each level, 10,000 realisations of damage are generated via Monte Carlo simulations,
542 recording the DS attained by each asset for each realisation. No correlation between the
543 occurrence of different DSs of the same asset (e.g., DS_{BP} and DS_{EFB} for tanks) or between the
544 occurrence of DSs of different assets (e.g., DS1 in pumps and DS1 in heat exchangers) is
545 assumed. More generally, no intra- or inter-asset correlation of capacities is assumed. One may
546 expect that identically designed, constructed, and maintained assets should be perfectly
547 correlated in their damage state capacities. Still, there are too many confounding factors.
548 “Identical” structures are often made of steel sourced from different material batches. Also, as
549 they age, it is common to replace parts or entire segments during standard maintenance. This
550 may result in two seemingly identical assets experiencing different damage when subjected to
551 the same ground motion. So, intuition suggests some positive correlation between capacities
552 of such assets, but certainly not a perfect one. For simplicity, and given the lack of data to
553 support selecting any specific value, we shall presently default to an assumption of zero
554 correlation and reserve a more thorough investigation for a future system-level risk study. To
555 account for uncertainty in the tank fill ratio, for all realisations we set the fill ratio of TK-01 to
556 60% and TK-03 to 90%, while random fill ratios are assigned to TK-02 and TK-04 for each
557 realisation. This approach is chosen to represent a realistic operating condition in the HDS unit.
558 Figure 16 shows the most frequent DS experienced by each asset for each *AvgSa* level.

559 At the lowest *AvgSa* level, the most likely outcome is no damage across all HDS unit assets
560 [Figure 16(a)], which is expected for a frequent serviceability-level event. However, some
561 damage may still occur, primarily affecting pumps, the separator (V-01), the ground-level heat
562 exchanger (E-01), tank TK-03, and the piping system. Even so, these components experience
563 damage in less than 20% of cases.

564 At the 10% in 50yrs *AvgSa* level, Figure 16(b) indicates that pumps, V-01, and E-01 frequently
565 experience anchorage failure, while the most common damage state for tank TK-03 is base
566 plate damage (DS_{BP}). Specifically, V-01 and E-01 undergo anchorage failure in over 80% of
567 cases, with pumps and TK-03 following at approximately 60%.

568 At the 5% in 50 years *AvgSa* level [Figure 16(c)], pumps, V-01, E-01, and the second-floor
569 heat exchangers (E-03A/B) predominantly experience anchorage failure, while tank TK-03
570 most frequently suffers base plate damage (DS_{BP}). At this level, V-01 and E-01 sustain
571 anchorage failure in over 90% of cases, while pumps, E-03A/B, and TK-03 experience some
572 form of damage more than 60% of the time.

573 At the highest *AvgSa* level [Figure 16(d)], acceleration-sensitive components—including
574 pumps, heat exchangers, and the separator—most commonly suffer anchorage failure. The
575 piping system frequently reaches DS3, indicating that at least one segment has exceeded its
576 ultimate strain limit. Additionally, tanks TK-01 and TK-03 predominantly experience DS_{BP} .
577 Notably, V-01 and E-01 are damaged in nearly 100% of cases, while pumps and E-03A/B
578 sustain damage in over 80% of cases.

579 From the fragility analysis, other than the equipment-supporting building and furnace (which
580 are considered rugged), the reactors (R-01/02) and the stripper (C-01) emerged as the least
581 vulnerable assets in the HDS unit.

582

583 Figure 16. Most frequent DSs experienced by assets subjected to *AvgSa* with: (a) 50% probability of
 584 exceedance in 50yrs; (b) 10% probability of exceedance in 50yrs; (c) 5% probability of exceedance in
 585 50yrs; (d) 2% probability of exceedance in 50yrs.

586 7 Conclusions

587 This study introduces a refined yet practical methodology for developing asset-specific hazard-
 588 consistent seismic fragility functions for interconnected components within an industrial
 589 facility's functional unit. This is the crucial step for conducting realistic earthquake risk and
 590 resilience assessments of industrial plants.

591 Such asset-specific fragility functions were analytically derived by analysing each structure
 592 individually, while accounting for nested components and internal non-structural elements.
 593 Specifically, a set of fragility functions was derived via Multiple Stripe Analysis with ground
 594 motion records selected to align with the site hazard conditions using the Conditional Spectrum
 595 method that hinged on a single ground motion intensity measure, namely *AvgSa*, carefully
 596 defined in a specific range of vibration periods, which is a reasonably good predictor of the
 597 response of all assets. The approach is refined by employing simple but sophisticated finite
 598 element models to evaluate the seismic response of the assets and by recognising their role in
 599 within an interconnected network. The practicality derives from using a single set of ground

600 motions for assessing the vulnerability of all assets, despite differences in their dynamic
601 properties and failure modes.

602 This collection of fragility functions offers a detailed perspective of the vulnerability of each
603 individual structure, allowing to track consequences specific to each asset, while providing a
604 unit-level view of the interconnected assets through the piping system. The fragility functions
605 for the piping system were derived to reflect the overall vulnerability of the network connecting
606 the pipe segments into a cohesive operational system.

607 To demonstrate the methodology, a hydrodesulphurisation unit of a typical crude oil refinery
608 in Greece, already presented in detail in the companion paper, was analysed. The unit included
609 liquid storage tanks, pumps, heat exchangers, an equipment-supporting building, a furnace,
610 reactors, a high temperature separator, a stripper, and a piping system. The fragility analysis
611 for this case study showed that the furnace and the industrial building are essentially rugged,
612 while liquid storage tanks, pumps, heat exchangers, high-temperature separator, and the piping
613 system are more vulnerable and may experience significant damage when exposed to seismic
614 loading. Even in low-to-moderate ground motions typical of low magnitude earthquakes, these
615 more fragile assets face a notable probability of damage, which is significant not only because
616 of the high repair or replacement costs but also because of the potential large economic losses
617 from operational disruptions.

618

619 **Acknowledgements**

620 The first author would like to sincerely thank EUCENTRE and IUSS Pavia for the funding
621 provided. Additional funding was provided by the European Union under Horizon-Europe
622 project PLOTO (Grant Agreement No. 101069941). Also, the authors would like to thank Prof.
623 Denis Sarigiannis and Mr. Achilleas Karakoltzidis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) for
624 their help in developing the case study and understanding the HDS operation, as well as Dr.
625 Nikolaos D. Karaferis (National Technical University of Athens) and Prof. Athanasia K.
626 Kazantzi (International Hellenic University) for their valuable support on the development of
627 some of the numerical models used in the study.

628

629 **Declaration of conflicting interests**

630 The authors declare no potential conflicting interests concerning the research, authorship,
631 and/or publication of this article.

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879

880 Figure A-1. Tanks MSA results per EDP (left: TK-01, TK-02, and TK-03; right: TK-04) at a 60% fill
 881 ratio: (a),(b) Height of sloshing wave for DS_{SL}; (c),(d) base plate rotation for DS_{BP}; (e),(f) wall
 882 meridional stress for DS_{EFB}. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines each
 883 damage state; it is not constant for DS_{EFB} as it changes with the ground motion and the intensity (the
 884 median values per stripe are shown) [d : maximum convective wave height, θ_{pl} : base plate rotation, σ_m :
 885 meridional stress of the tank's shell].

886

887 Figure A-2. Tanks MSA results per EDP (left: TK-01, TK-02, and TK-03; right: TK-04) at a 30% fill
 888 ratio: (a),(b) Height of sloshing wave for DS_{SL} ; (c),(d) base plate rotation for DS_{BP} ; (e),(f) wall
 889 meridional stress for DS_{EFB} . The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines each
 890 damage state; it is not constant for DS_{EFB} as it changes with the ground motion and the intensity (the
 891 median values per stripe are shown) [d : maximum convective wave height, θ_{pl} : base plate rotation, σ_m :
 892 meridional stress of the tank's shell].

893

894 Figure A-3. Pump MSA results per EDP: (a) PCA for DS1 in x direction; (b) PCA for DS1 in y direction.
 895 The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines DS1 [PCA: Peak Component
 896 Acceleration].

897

898 Figure A-4. Equipment-supporting building MSA results. Only the median threshold for DS1 is shown,
 899 as the structure stays well below even at high intensities [IDR: Interstorey Drift Ratio].

900

901 Figure A-5. Heat exchangers MSA results per EDP (PCA) for DS1: (a) E-01 in x direction; (b) E-01 in
 902 y direction; (c) E-02A&B in x direction; (d) E-02A&B in y direction; (e) E-03A&B in x direction; (f)
 903 E-03A&B in y direction. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines DS1 [PCA:
 904 Peak Component Acceleration].

905

906 Figure A-6. Furnace MSA results per EDP (first set of DSs): (a) TDR for DS1; (b) IDR for DS2; (c) R_c
 907 for DS3. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines each damage state [TDR:
 908 Top Drift Ratio, IDR: Interstorey Drift Ratio; R_c : buckling parameter].

909

910 Figure A-7. Furnace MSA results per EDP (second set of DSs): (a) PCA for DS1 in x direction; (b) PCA
 911 for DS1 in y direction. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines DS1 [PCA:
 912 Peak Component Acceleration].

913

914 Figure A-8. Reactor and stripper MSA results per EDP: (a) TDR for DS1; (b) R_c for DS2. The vertical
 915 lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines each damage state [TDR: Top Drift Ratio, R_c :
 916 buckling parameter].

917

918 Figure A-9. High temperature separator MSA results per EDP: (a) PCA for DS1 in x direction; (b) PCA
 919 for DS1 in y direction. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines DS1 [PCA:
 920 Peak Component Acceleration].

921

922 Figure A-10. Piping system MSA results (tensile failure) per EDP (axial strain): (a) 6" piping; (b) 10"
 923 piping; (c) 12" piping; (d) 24" piping. The vertical lines represent the median EDP threshold that defines
 924 each damage state.

925

926 Figure A-11. Piping system MSA results (compressive/buckling failure) per EDP (axial strain): (a) 6"
 927 piping; (b) 10" piping; (c) 12" piping; (d) 24" piping. The vertical lines represent the median EDP
 928 threshold that defines each damage state; the median EDP threshold corresponding to DS2 and DS3 for
 929 the 6" piping coincide and are therefore plotted overlapping.